

SIGNED TOTAL ROMAN DOMINATION OF COMPLETE SPLIT GRAPHS

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Abstract: In this paper, we investigate the concept of signed total Roman domination (STRD) in the context of complete split graphs. Domination in graph theory is a well-studied area with numerous variants, each imposing different constraints on how vertices dominate or are dominated by others. The signed total Roman domination is a recently introduced variant that combines elements of signed domination and Roman domination, incorporating both vertex labeling and edge-based conditions. Optimal value for complete split graph is equal to 3, which is proved using integer linear programming.

Keywords: Graphs, Domination, Signed Total Roman Domination, Complete split graphs

1. INTRODUCTION

Problem of Roman domination was introduced in context of military strategy concerning defence of Roman Empire in the time of famous emperor Constantine the Great. Falling fortunes of Roman empire during the 4th century AD needed accepting new defensive strategy in depth. To much legions in one province could lead to rebellion and rise of pretenders for the imperial purple and to small military detachments meant that province was undefended. Solution strategy, considered in papers (ReVelle and Rosing, 2000) and (Stewart, 1999), required that in any province there are 0, 1 or 2 legions. Province was considered defended if it has inside its border at least 1 legion or that in some neighboring province were stationed 2 legions. Naturally, goal was to defend the whole Empire with as small number of legions as possible.

Mathematically, in graph interpretation, Roman Empire could be represented as a graph, where provinces are vertices and edges exist if the provinces have common border or well traveled sea rout between them. Now, problem of Roman domination (RDP) could be interpreted as follows:

For a given simple graph $G(V, E)$, find $\min \sum_{v \in V} f(v)$, where Roman dominating function $f : V \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2\}$ subject to that for every v such that $f(v) = 0$, there exists at least one of its adjacent vertex w such that $f(w) = 2$.

There are many modifications of the problem of Roman domination in literature. In this paper we will consider problem of signed total Roman domination (STRDP) introduced in (Volkman, 2016b). In graph terms STRDP can be formulated as follows:

For a given simple graph $G(V, E)$, find $\min \sum_{v \in V} f(v)$, where signed total Roman dominating function $f : V \rightarrow \{-1, 1, 2\}$ subject to that for every vertex v its adjacent vertices called open neighborhood and denoted as $N(v)$, must satisfy $\sum_{w \in N(v)} f(w) \geq 1$, and every vertex u for which $f(u) = -1$ is adjacent to at least one vertex v for which $f(v) = 2$. This minimum is denoted $\gamma_{stR}(G)$.

Instead of Roman domination, signed Roman domination problems emphasize the risk of attack on the province where there is no legion but some small detachments commonly called auxiliary troops. This signed modification is more realistic than just indicating that in a province there are no troops and putting the value of that vertex by 0. Indicating that in the province is small garrison by putting -1 make it defense more demanding.

In this paper we will consider solving STRDP on special class of graphs - complete split graphs.

Complete split graphs $K_{k, n-k}^*$ are defined as simple graphs $G(V, E)$ where n is the order of graph i.e. $|V| = n$. Formally, $V_1 = \{v_i | 1 \leq i \leq k\}$, $V_2 = \{v_i | k+1 \leq i \leq n\}$, $V = V_1 \cup V_2$, $F_1 = \{v_i v_j | 1 \leq i < j \leq k\}$, $F_2 = \{v_i v_j | 1 \leq i \leq k, k+1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E = F_1 \cup F_2$. In other words set V is partitioned in 2 subsets V_1 and V_2 where $|V_1| = k$, $|V_2| = n - k$, $V_1 \cup V_2 = V$ and $V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset$. Graph induced by subset V_1 is a clique, while vertices from V_2 are adjacent only to vertices from V_1 , and $deg(v) = \begin{cases} n-1, & v \in V_1 \\ k, & v \in V_2 \end{cases}$.

Example. $K_{3,3}^*$ is given on the following figure with optimal solution of STRDP given by numbers attached to all vertices.

Figure 1: Signed total Roman domination for $K_{3,3}^*$

2. PREVIOUS WORKS

Literature on Roman domination is huge and is growing over years so it is out of scope of this paper. Similarly, there is more than 15 modifications of Roman domination problem so, only introduction papers are numbered over 20 and this also is out of scope of this paper. We will limit previous work only on papers directly linked to STRDP.

In paper (Volkman, 2016b) STRDP is introduced and is discussed. As modification of RDP it is also NP hard. Additionally, the author presented optimal solution for some classes of graphs, notably: stars, complete graphs, complete bipartite graphs $K_{p,p}$, cycles and paths.

The same author is broadening research of STRDP problem in (Volkman, 2016a). Author introduces some new concepts. First, a set $\{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_d\}$ of distinct signed total Roman dominating functions on G with the property that $\sum_{i=1}^d f_i(v) \leq 1$ for each $v \in V(G)$, is called a *signed total Roman dominating family (of functions) on G* . The maximum number of functions in a signed total Roman dominating family on G is the *signed total Roman domatic number of G* , denoted by $d_{stR}(G)$. Author presented sharp bounds for $\gamma_{stR}(G)$ and $d_{stR}(G)$. In addition, the total signed Roman domatic number of some graphs is determined.

The following paper (Volkman, 2017) presents research of STRDP in another direction, that is on the digraphs $D(V, E)$. In the paper are given bounds on $\gamma_{stR}(D)$, and also signed total Roman domination on some classes of digraphs.

Another approach for solving STRDP is given in (Filipović et al., 2022). For each problem authors proposed two integer linear programming (ILP) formulations, the constraint programming (CP) formulation and variable neighborhood search (VNS) method. Additionally, proofs for the correctness of the ILP formulations and a polyhedral study in which was shown that the polyhedrons of the two model relaxations are equivalent.

Also, for solving STRDP, VNS uses specifically designed penalty function that allows the appearance of slightly infeasible solutions. All proposed approaches were tested on the large number of instances. Experimental results indicate that all of them reach optimal solutions for the most of small and middle scale instances. Both ILP models have proven to be more successful than the other two methods.

3. NEW RESULTS

Let us now consider complete split graphs $K_{k,n-k}^*$ where $k \geq 2, n - k \geq 2$. We define the following integer variables:

- $x_1 = |\{u \in V_1 | f(u) = -1\}|$;
- $x_2 = |\{u \in V_2 | f(u) = -1\}|$;
- $y_1 = |\{u \in V_1 | f(u) = 1\}|$;
- $y_2 = |\{u \in V_2 | f(u) = 1\}|$;
- $z_1 = |\{u \in V_1 | f(u) = 2\}|$;
- $z_2 = |\{u \in V_2 | f(u) = 2\}|$.

Let us consider following integer linear program (ILP):

$$\min -x_1 - x_2 + y_1 + y_2 + 2z_1 + 2z_2 \tag{1}$$

subject to:

$$-x_1 - x_2 + y_1 + y_2 + 2(z_1 - 1) + 2z_2 \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

$$-x_1 + y_1 + 2z_1 \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

$$-x_1 - x_2 + (y_1 - 1) + y_2 + 2z_1 + 2z_2 \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

$$-x_1 + y_1 + 2z_1 \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

$$-(x_1 - 1) - x_2 + y_1 + y_2 + 2z_1 + 2z_2 \geq 1 \quad (6)$$

$$-x_1 + y_1 + 2z_1 \geq 1 \quad (7)$$

$$x_1 + x_2 \leq nz_1 \quad (8)$$

$$x_2 \leq kz_2 \quad (9)$$

$$x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2, \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \cup \{0\} \quad (10)$$

Term (1) is equal to $\min_{v \in V} f(v)$. Inequalities (2-7) correspond to fact that in every open neighborhood $\sum_{w \in N(v)} f(w)$ must be greater or equal to 1. Inequalities (2) and (3) correspond to vertices with $f(v) = 2$, inequalities (4) and (5) correspond to vertices with $f(v) = 1$ and inequalities (6) and (7) correspond to vertices with $f(v) = -1$.

Let us show that if there is $v \in V_1$ such that $f(v) = -1$ than in optimal solution there must be at least one vertex $w \in V_1$ such that $f(w) = 2$. This situation corresponds to $x_1 \geq 0, x_2 = z_1 = 0$ and $z_2 > 0$.

Since $x_1 > 0$ and $z_1 = 0$ there must be at least one vertex $v \in V_2$ such that $f(v) = 2$. Without loss of generality we can assign $f(v_{k+1}) = 2$.

Since $x_2 = 0$ $\min_{v \in V_2} f(v) = n - k + 1$ which implies $f(v_{k+2}) = \dots = f(v_n) = 1$. We will consider two cases: when k is odd and when k is even.

$$k = 2m + 1:$$

Then $\min_{v \in V_1} f(v) = 1$ (it follows from condition $\min_{w \in N(v), v \in V_2} f(w) \geq 1$) which implies, without loss of generality, $f(v_1) = \dots = f(v_{m+1}) = 1$ and $f(v_{m+2}) = \dots = f(v_k) = -1$. It is easy to see that if we assign $f(v_1) = 2$ and $f(v_{k+2}) = -1$ then all conditions for STRDP will be satisfied and objective function will be lower. Which proves our statement.

$$k = 2m:$$

Similarly as in case when k is odd, $\min_{v \in V_1} f(v) = 2$ which implies $f(v_1) = \dots = f(v_{m+1}) = 1$ and $f(v_{m+2}) = \dots = f(v_k) = -1$. There is $m + 1$ vertices with $f(v) = 1$ and $m - 1$ vertices with $f(v) = -1$. Again, if we assign $f(v_1) = 2$ and $f(v_{k+2}) = -1$ then all conditions for STRDP will be satisfied and objective function will be lower. Which proves our statement.

Inequality (8) implies that in the open neighborhood of the vertex $v \in V_1$ $f(v) = -1$ there must be at least one vertex w with $f(w) = 2$.

Let us show that if there is $v \in V_2$ such that $f(v) = -1$ than in optimal solution there must be at least one vertex $w \in V_2$ such that $f(w) = 2$. This situation corresponds to $x_2 \geq 0, x_1 = z_2 = 0$ and $z_1 > 0$.

Since $x_2 > 0$ and $z_1 = 0$ there must be at least one vertex $v \in V_1$ such that $f(v) = 2$. Without loss of generality we can assign $f(v_1) = 2$.

$$\text{Since } x_1 = 0 \text{ } \min_{v \in V_1} f(v) = k + 1 \text{ which implies } f(v_2) = \dots = f(v_k) = 1.$$

$$\text{Let us consider three cases: } n > 2k - 2, n = 2k - 2 \text{ and } n < 2k - 2.$$

$$n > 2k - 2:$$

Since in V_1 there is $k - 1$ vertices with $f(v) = 1$ in V_2 maximum number of vertices with $f(v) = -1$ is $k - 2$. This is required so that $\sum_{w \in N(v), v \in V_1} f(w) \geq 1$. Since $n > 2k - 2$, it follows that $n - k > k - 2$ which implies there is at least one vertex $v \in V_2$ such that $f(v) = 1$. Without loss of generality let it be v_{k+1} .

Now, if we assign $f(v_2) = -1$ and $f(v_{k+1}) = 2$ then all conditions for STRDP will be satisfied and objective function will be lower, which proves our statement.

$n = 2k - 2$: Since in V_1 there is $k - 1$ vertices with $f(v) = 1$ in V_2 maximum number of vertices with $f(v) = -1$ is $k - 2$. This is required so that $\sum_{w \in N(v), v \in V_1} f(w) \geq 1$. Since $n = 2k - 2$, it is not necessary that in V_2 there is v such that $f(v) = 1$. This implies that all vertices v in V_2 can have $f(v) = -1$. Now we can assign without loss of generality for $k \geq 5$, $f(v_2) = f(v_3) = f(v_4) = -1$, and $f(v_{k+1}) = f(v_{k+2}) = 2$ (in V_1 there is $k - 4$ vertices with $f(v) = 1$ and in V_2 there is $k - 4$ vertices with $f(v) = -1$). All conditions for STRDP will be satisfied and objective function will be equal, and though objective functions are equal our statement holds.

$n < 2k - 2$: Since in V_1 there is $k - 1$ vertices with $f(v) = 1$ in V_2 maximum number of vertices with $f(v) = -1$ is $k - 3$. This is required so that $\sum_{w \in N(v), v \in V_1} f(w) \geq 1$. Since $n < 2k - 2$, it is not necessary that in V_2 there is v such that $f(v) = 1$. This implies that all vertices v in V_2 can have $f(v) = -1$. Now we can assign without loss of generality, $f(v_2) = f(v_3) = -1$, and $f(v_{k+1}) = 2$ (in V_1 there is $k - 3$ vertices with $f(v) = 1$ and

in V_2 there is $k - 4$ vertices with $f(v) = -1$. All conditions for STRDP will be satisfied and objective function is lower and our statement holds.

Similarly, inequality (9) implies that in the open neighborhood of the vertex $v \in V_2$ with $f(v) = -1$ there must be at least one vertex w with $f(w) = 2$.

On close inspection conditions (3), (5) and (7) are identical so two of these are redundant. Also, conditions (2), (4) and (6) can be transformed into:

$$-x_1 - x_2 + y_1 + y_2 + 2z_1 + 2z_2 \geq 3 \quad (11)$$

$$-x_1 - x_2 + y_1 + y_2 + 2z_1 + 2z_2 \geq 2 \quad (12)$$

$$-x_1 - x_2 + y_1 + y_2 + 2z_1 + 2z_2 \geq 0 \quad (13)$$

From this it is easy to see that if condition (11) is satisfied then both conditions (12) and (13) are satisfied so they are also redundant. Since we are considering complete split graph it holds $x_1 + y_1 + z_1 = k$ and $x_2 + y_2 + z_2 = n - k$, i.e. $x_1 = k - y_1 - z_1$ and $x_2 = n - k - y_2 - z_2$. Now, if we include them in conditions (1), (2), (3) (8), (9) and (10), we obtain following new ILP model:

$$\min -n + 2y_1 + 2y_2 + 3z_1 + 3z_2 \quad (14)$$

subject to:

$$2y_1 + 3z_1 \geq 1 + k \quad (15)$$

$$2y_1 + 2y_2 + 3z_1 + 3z_2 \geq 3 + n \quad (16)$$

$$y_1 + y_2 + (n + 1)z_1 + z_2 \geq n \quad (17)$$

$$y_2 + (k + 1)z_2 \geq n - k \quad (18)$$

$$y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2, \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \cup \{0\} \quad (19)$$

With this new ILP model we can now prove following theorem for $K_{k,n-k}^*$.

Theorem. For $k \geq 3$ and $n \geq 4$, it holds $\gamma_{STR}(K_{k,n-k}^*) = 3$.

Proof. Cases $k = 3, k = 4$ and $n = 4, n = 5, n = 6$ can be directly proved. Let $k \geq 5$ and $n \geq k + 2$. Let us consider dual problem of the program (14)-(19). Denoting the dual variables u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 we obtain

$$\max -n + (1 + k)u_1 + (3 + n)u_2 + nu_3 + (n - k)u_4 \quad (20)$$

subject to:

$$2u_1 + 2u_2 + u_3 \leq 2 \quad (21)$$

$$2u_2 + u_3 + u_4 \leq 2 \quad (22)$$

$$3u_1 + 3u_2 + (n + 1)u_3 \leq 3 \quad (23)$$

$$3u_2 + u_3 + (k + 1)u_4 \leq 3 \quad (24)$$

$$u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4 \geq 0 \quad (25)$$

In the primal problem $x_1 + x_2$ must be greater than 1, since if $x_1 = x_2 = 0$ means that $y_1 + y_2 + z_1 + z_2 = n$ implying that objective function in (14) has value at least n , which is obviously not minimum equal to 3.

So, we conclude that $x_1 + x_2 \geq 1$ and this implies from constraint (8) that $z_1 \geq 1$. Now, since $z_1 \in \mathbb{Z}$ we can obtain conclusion that constraint (17) can be interpreted as $y_1 + y_2 + (n + 1)z_1 + z_2 \geq n + 1 > n$. It means that in complementary slackness condition $u_3(y_1 + y_2 + (n + 1)z_1 + z_2 - n) = 0$ dual variable u_3 must be equal to 0.

From dual constraint (21) we obtain that $u_1 + u_2 \leq 1$. Since coefficients by u_1 and u_2 in the dual objective function are $1 + k$ and $3 + n$ respectively, and $3 + n > 1 + k$ for any n and k we can concluded that in optimal solution for the dual problem must be $u_1 = 0$ and $u_2 = 1$.

From complementary slackness condition $u_2(2y_1 + 2y_2 + 3z_1 + 3z_2 - 3 - n) = 0$ follows that $2y_1 + 2y_2 + 3z_1 + 3z_2 = 3 + n$ which gives us primal and dual objective function optimal value equal to 3.

Finally, since $\gamma_{STR}(K_{k,n-k}^*)$ is equal to minimum of (1) we conclude that $\gamma_{STR}(K_{k,n-k}^*) = 3$. ◀

It is interesting to see what happens in degenerated cases when $k = 1$ or $n - k = 1$. If $n - k = 1$ graph is clique K_n , with $\gamma_{STR}(K_n) = 3$ (Volkman, 2016b). When $k = 1$, graph is star S_{n-1} with $\gamma_{STR}(S_{n-1}) = 3$ (Volkman, 2016b).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper signed total Roman domination of complete split graphs are considered. Exact value is equal to 3, for $k \geq 2$ and $n - k \geq 2$. The result is obtained by solving integer linear programming formulation with 4 variables and 4 constraints.

Future investigations could be directed towards studying signed total Roman domination across various graph classes, along with examining analogous graph invariants in the context of complete split graphs.

LITERATURE

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